

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN VIRTUAL AND VISUAL AESTHETIC PERCEPTION OF THE WORLD

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Abstract: Today, the science of aesthetics has a wide influence on the spiritual, educational, social and economic spheres of society. It is an expression of this. Studying the aesthetic taste and aesthetics of the society means improving the human spirituality and culture, developing the market economy, supply and demand, market economy and marketing, determining management tolerance, and simultaneously improving the quality of life.

Key words: Aesthetics, Aesthetics of nature, Aesthetics of technology, design, Sports Aesthetics, Aesthetics of life, archetypes, intellect, will-will, emotion, ethics, Poetics.

¹Aesthetics is a science that studies the emotional perception of the world. Aesthetics studies the subjective perception of art, culture, and nature. Aesthetics belongs to the field of axiology of philosophy. The term "aesthetics" was introduced into scientific circulation by the German philosopher A. Baumgarten (1714-1776). The expressions philosophy of beauty, philosophy of art, philosophy of artistic creation are used as synonyms of aesthetics. In recent times, the terms aestheticism or philosophy of sophistication have also come to mean Aesthetics. Aesthetics includes art Aesthetics, natural Aesthetics, technical Aesthetics, design, sports Aesthetics, lifestyle Aesthetics, environmental beautification, and others.

¹Aesthetics-Ancient Greek: aísthēsis? German: Ästhetik - "feeling", "feeling".

Aesthetics deals with such categories as sophistication, taste, beauty, ugliness, grandeur, depravity, tragedy, ridiculousness, wonder, fantasy. The concept of sophistication occupies a special place among them. On the one hand, it includes all aspects of aesthetic perception (aesthetic feeling, 2aesthetic pleasure, aesthetic taste, 3aesthetic discussion, etc.), on the other hand, aesthetic properties - practical beauty, grandeur, tragic, funny, etc. includes aspects. With this next aspect, elegance is sometimes considered as a subject of Aesthetics.

Among the research objects of aesthetics, art occupies a special place, it is the most studied aesthetic field from ancient times to the present day. Aesthetics differs from art studies in that it approaches its object philosophically. Aesthetics studies art in a holistic system consisting of the artist, the work of art, the person who perceives the work of art, and develops the general laws necessary for all types of art. For example, the theory of rhyme in literature cannot be applied to music or sculpture. The theory of composition or style in aesthetics applies to all forms of art, from architecture to fine art photography. Meanwhile, Aesthetics explores the nature of art, its creativity, and other aspects; studies the essence of artistic currents and trends, creative styles.

Aesthetics or aesthetics is one of the oldest sciences. Its history spans two and a half to three thousand years. However, it got its current name in the 18th century. The great German philosopher Alexander Baumgarten (1714-1762) was the first to introduce the term "aesthetics" into scientific circulation. In this, he reacted based on the teaching of another great German philosopher G. Leibniz (1646-1716). and emphasizes that each of them should be studied from a separate philosophical point of view. Until Baumgarten, the science that studies intelligence - logic, and the science that studies will - ethics (ethics) had a place in philosophy for a long time. However, the science that studies emotions did not have its own name in the philosophical status.

²Aesthetic pleasure is defined as "the feeling of art or beauty" in Uzbek. This emotion refers to the human ability to understand and value beauty, humor, and thought

³Aesthetic discussion is defined as "beauty assessment" in Uzbek language. This is the process of expressing and defining opinions and values among people on art, music, literature and other types of art.

Baumgarten's contribution in this regard is that he took the phrase "aesthetics" (from the German "aesthetic" - "aesthetic") from the Greek word *aisthetikos* - "oyestetikos", which means "to feel", "to feel", "to be felt", filled that gap.

The origins of the history of aesthetics can be traced back to Sumerian (Sumerian), Babylonian, ancient Egyptian, ancient Chinese, and later Greek myths. 5-6 thousand years ago, the first writing - mixed script, was reflected in the words "beauty", "art", "music". In ancient Egypt, 4-4.5 thousand years before Christ, all the main types of art appeared, and a little later professional theater.⁴The aesthetic ideas advanced by Avesta, the holy book of Zoroastrian religion, later influenced the development of aesthetics in India and then in Greece. Aesthetic ideas in the ancient East were first formed on the basis of the principles of utility (what is useful is beautiful), then morality (what is good is beautiful). Representatives of Greek classical aesthetics, especially Aristotle, mentioned that beauty can exist separately from utility and goodness; in this regard, his work "Poetics" ("The Art of Poetry") is noteworthy. In the Middle Ages, Eastern Muslim Sufism Aesthetics perfected these ideas and raised them to a new level; It served as a theoretical basis for the development of Renaissance and New Age Aesthetics. It can be clearly seen in the legacy of aesthetics by Descartes, D. Hume, I. Kant and others. For example, 3 of Kant's famous 4 principles of beauty are based on the theories of Eastern philosophers. These 3 principles are that beauty is based on a disinterested attitude; that he is the object of love that has become a necessity (Ghazali); the fact that we cannot know beauty through a simple logical approach (Pharaoobi) led Kant to create the 4th principle that beauty manifests itself for us not in the form of a goal, but in the form of appropriateness. After Kant, the theories of Schiller, Schelling, and Hegel in German rational aesthetics became more important for the development of aesthetics. In the

aesthetic views of non-rational philosophers such as Schopenhauer, Nietzsche, and Dilthey, unique new ideas were put forward, for

⁴Zoroastrianism is one of the oldest religions, and this religion appeared in the VII-VI centuries BC in Central Asia - Khorazm oasis. His prophet Zarathustra was a historical figure.

example, Schopenhauer introduced a new category of "interest" to Aesthetics, while Nietzsche proposed to study art by dividing it into two types - Apollonian and Dionysian. In the Aesthetics of the latest era, Z. Freud, especially in the teachings of K. Jung, the study of the relationship between the work of art and the artist on the basis of mental types was a new step forward. Also, J.P. Sartre, A. Camus, G. Marcel, H. Ortega i Gaset and other thinkers were interested in the issues of beauty and destiny of art in industrial society. In the scaling process of current Aesthetics, serious attention is also paid to the Aesthetics of technology, nature and life; the problem of moral beauty began to occupy a more important place.

Each science has its own practical importance in the life of a person and society. Aesthetics is no exception. Our science, first of all, is of great importance in terms of correct education of sophistication in our daily life. Every member of our free, democratic society should have an elegant taste that deeply feels beauty and preserves it; they should be able to distinguish between a real work of art and a low-level work, and reject "public art". From this point of view, Aesthetics is important for all members of society.

Aesthetics is of great practical importance, especially for creators of works of art. For example, an artist creating in a certain art form must first of all be a connoisseur of his field. Let's say that the composer, without knowing the notes, without knowing the rules of creating a musical work, including the general laws of aesthetics that apply to music, is unlikely to create a more orderly work. Some people have the wrong idea that genius artists create even without rules. Indeed, the geniuses themselves were often engaged in the theory of sophistication. As an example, it is enough to remember the names of such greats as ⁵Jami, Navoi, Leonardo da Vinci, Schiller, ⁶Chopin.

It is necessary to know Aesthetics for scientists, art critics and literary critics who study the work of art. Let's say that an art critic who knows only "pure theater" - stage art, no matter how talented he is, cannot conduct research at a high level of demand, or even write a noteworthy article. For example, he is not aware of dramaturgy, music, rules of style and composition, in a word, the laws of aesthetics. As a result, his research, article or review will be one-sided, devoid of philosophical generalizations, consisting of a collection of empty and shallow sentences.

Summary

To sum up, today there are several views on the origin of the science of aesthetics. In our opinion, the origin of this science is the result of humanity's aesthetic need for beauty. In its origin, synergetics (in the creation of harmony from chaos), rational mind and intuitive factors (based on mental and emotional), traditions and rituals of peoples, customs, creative process and works of great personalities, archetypes (collective unconscious), game we believe that theory, mimesis (imitation) and labor occupy an important place. Also, the science of aesthetics was gradually formed and developed through life experiences, skills, and knowledge acquired by a person.

⁵Jami (pseudonym; real name Nuriddin Abdurrahman ibn Ahmad) (November 7, 1414, Jam - November 9, 1492, Herat) is a Persian-Tajik poet, a prominent representative of the Naqshbandi order.

⁶Frédéric François Chopin (Fryderyk Franciszek Chopin; March 1, 1810 – October 17, 1849) was a Polish composer and virtuoso pianist of the Romantic period, who wrote mainly works for solo piano.

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